

Cyclopeptide alkaloids of *Zizyphus xylopyra*

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Abstract : 14-Membered cyclopeptide alkaloids, franganine, frangufoline, amphibine-D and mauritine-A has been isolated from the whole plant of *Zizyphus xylopyra* and their structures established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these alkaloids from *Z. xylopyra*.

Keywords : *Zizyphus xylopyra*, alkaloid, cyclopeptide.

Introduction

Zizyphus xylopyra Willd.¹ (Rhamnaceae) is distributed throughout India. A number of cyclopeptide alkaloids, viz. nummularine-B², -K² and -P², xylopyrine-A³, -B³, -C⁴, -D⁵, -E⁵ and -F⁶ have earlier been reported from this plant. In continuation of our work on *Zizyphus* species³⁻⁶, we report here the isolation of four more cyclopeptide alkaloids franganine⁷, frangufoline⁸, amphibine-D⁹ and mauritine-A⁹ from *Z. xylopyra*. These alkaloids were fully characterised. This is the first report of the occurrence of these compounds from this plant.

Experimental

Dried whole plant (3 kg) was powdered and repeatedly extracted with a mixture of C₆H₆-NH₄OH-MeOH (100 : 1 : 1). The total extract was concentrated to remove methanol and ammonia and extracted with 7% aqueous citric acid. The acidic solution was basified with ammonia and extracted with CHCl₃ which gave a mixture of crude alkaloids (3.0 g). The crude alkaloidal fraction was chromatographed over silica gel column eluting with a mixture of CHCl₃ and MeOH. The eluates from CHCl₃-MeOH (40 : 1), (30 : 1), (25 : 1) and (20 : 1) after purification with preparative TLC with solvents CHCl₃-MeOH (10 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH (8 : 1) and crystallisation from MeOH furnished respectively, franganine (1) as colourless needles (10 mg), m.p. 245–247 °C, [α]_D²⁰ – 300° (c 0.15, MeOH), frangufoline (2) as colourless granules (18 mg), m.p. 240–242 °C, [α]_D²⁰ – 245° (c 0.20, MeOH), amphibine-D (3) as colourless amorphous solid (21 mg), [α]_D²⁰ – 204° (c 0.09, MeOH) and mauritine-A

(4) as colourless small needles (16 mg), m.p. 103–104 °C, [α]_D²⁰ – 310° (c 0.18, MeOH).

1 : R₁ = R₂ = -CH₂CH(CH₃)₂
2 : R₁ = -CH₂CH(CH₃)₂, R₂ = -CH₂Ph

3 : R₁ = R₂ = -CH(CH₃)CH₂CH₃, R₃ = -CH₂Ph
4 : R₁ = -CH₂Ph, R₂ = -CH(CH₃)₂, R₃ = -CH₃

The spectral data of the above mentioned compounds are given below :

Compound 1 : UV (MeOH) λ_{max} strong end absorption and a weak shoulder at 325 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{max} 3280 (-NH), 2850 (-CH), 2780 (-NCH₃), 1640 (sec. amide), 1615 (-C=C-), 1250 cm⁻¹ (phenol ether); MS : m/z 500.3342 [M⁺] (HRMS, C₂₈H₄₄N₄O₄; calcd. 500.3362), 499, 485, 471, 457, 443, 387, 344, 303, 274, 210, 190,

182, 135, 115, 114 (base peak), 97, 72. Compound 1 (6 mg) was hydrolysed with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube at 120° for 20 h. Co-PC (*n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) of the hydrolysate exhibited three ninhydrin positive spots which were identified as leucine, β -hydroxyleucine and *N,N*-dimethylleucine by comparison with authentic samples.

Compound 2 : UV (MeOH) λ_{\max} strong end absorption and a shoulder at 225 (log ϵ 2.85) nm; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3260 (-NH), 2840 (-CH), 2780 (-NCH₃), 1680 and 1630 (sec. amide), 1610 (-C=C-), 1210 cm⁻¹ (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 534.3240 [M⁺] (HRMS, C₃₁H₄₂N₄O₄; calcd. 534.3205), 443, 387, 344, 303, 274, 210, 195, 190, 182, 167, 148 (base peak), 135, 97. Compound 2 (5 mg) was hydrolysed with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube at 120° for 20 h. Co-PC (*n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) of the hydrolysate exhibited three ninhydrin positive spots which were identified as leucine, β -hydroxyleucine and *N,N*-dimethylphenylalanine by comparison with authentic samples.

Compound 3 : UV (MeOH) λ_{\max} strong end absorption and weak shoulder at 250 and 280 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3365 (-NH), 2790 (-NCH₃), 1680 and 1635 (sec. amide), 1220 cm⁻¹ (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 631.3770 [M⁺] (HRMS, C₃₆H₄₉N₅O₅; calcd. 631.3733), 602, 540, 484, 482, 370, 344, 343, 342, 289, 274, 261, 229, 209, 203, 186, 181, 148 (base peak), 135, 96, 86, 68. Compound 3 (6 mg) was hydrolysed with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube at 120° for 20 h. Co-PC (*n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) of the hydrolysate with authentic amino acids exhibited two ninhydrin positive spots identified as isoleucine and *N,N*-dimethylphenylalanine.

Compound 4 : UV (MeOH) λ_{\max} strong end absorption and weak shoulder at 203 nm; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} 3395 (-NH), 2960–2820 (-CH), 2790 (-NCH₃), 1660 and 1620 (sec.

amide), 1220, 1040 cm⁻¹ (phenol ether); MS : *m/z* 575.3157 [M⁺] (HRMS, C₃₂H₄₁N₅O₅; calcd. 575.3107), 574, 532, 530, 518, 504, 502, 461, 378, 377, 376, 328, 308, 243, 229, 221, 215, 199, 186, 171, 135, 96, 72 (base peak). Compound 4 (7 mg) was hydrolysed with 6 *N* HCl in a sealed tube at 120° for 20 h. Co-PC (*n*-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) of the hydrolysate with authentic amino acids using ninhydrin as spraying reagent exhibited the presence of three amino acids phenylalanine, *N,N*-dimethylalanine and valine.

The structures of all the above compounds were confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR) available in the Department.

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